

Recreational Activities of Public Elementary School Teachers in Bayambang, Division of Pangasinan I Relation to Health Benefits

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Abstract

This study determined the extent to which public elementary school teachers of Bayambang Division of Pangasinan I engaged in recreational activities in relation to health benefits during the school year 2025 – 2026.

The salient findings of the study: The teachers moderately engaged in both indoor activities and outdoor activities of recreation; The recreational activities were highly beneficial to physical and emotional aspects; moderately beneficial in social and mental aspects; There was a very high correlation between the health benefits of the teachers gained in performing indoor recreational activities and outdoor recreational activities; The problems encountered by the respondent teachers along recreational activities were described as moderately serious; The proposed plan of action can be formulated.

The following conclusion were drawn from the findings of the study: The teachers have not reached the desired extent of engaging recreational activities; The teachers found the recreational activities beneficial to their physical, social, mental and emotional well-being; The health benefits aimed from indoor recreational activities and outdoor recreational activities were related to each other; The formulated action plan could improve the extent of teachers engage in recreational activities in relation to health benefits.

Keywords: *recreational activities, public elementary teachers, health benefits, indoor activities, outdoor activities, physical health, emotional well-being, social benefits, mental health, Bayambang Pangasinan*

Chapter 1 THE PROBLEM

Rationale

Recreation is a voluntary participation in an activity during free and unobligated time that gives enjoyment. It refreshes one's mind and body after a day's work. Recreation embraces both indoor and outdoor activities that refer to sports and exercise leading to the attainment of enjoyment as well as managing our desired weight.

Indoor recreational activities are undertaken on the comfort of one's home or more specifically indoor and they are to recreate the mind and soul. For such indoor recreation activities, there are well-established clubs or recreation centers that have well-equipped indoor leisure facilities, which cater for sports activities for all ages and abilities, but it can be done just at home for simple activities. These activities help you relax and give soothing effect to your nerves and release the tension and maintain equilibrium.

(<https://www.scribd.com/document/12314780/Indoor-Recreational-Activities>)

Outdoor recreation or outdoor activity refers to leisure pursuits engaged in the outdoors, often in natural or semi-natural out of town. The outdoors as a physical or social setting may meet the needs of physical health, self-sufficiency, risk-taking, the building of social ties, and the needs of achievement (such as participating, enhancing and challenging skills, testing stamina and endurance, and seeking adventure or excitement. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Outdoor_recreation

The world today is confronted with a number of serious health and social issues – obesity, diabetes, depression and suicide to name a few. The trend towards a sedentary lifestyle is recognized as a major contributor towards many of world's health and social issues. With the increased awareness of these issues, park and recreation professionals, policy makers, health care providers, public safety officers and educators need to better understand the benefits that park and recreation lands, facilities and programs may play in addressing these concerns. Healthcare and recreation professionals realize they must make physical activity fund, safe and accessible to address these alarming health trends. They need to make recreation opportunities more available while actively promoting the link between parks and recreation and better mental, physical and societal health. (OELD's library. <http://stats.decd.org.retrieved2013-12-12>)

In addition, the Philippines is currently facing major health issues with alarming increases in the prevalence of hypertension, obesity, and physical inactivity according to national data (Food and Nutrition Research Institute, Department of Science and Technology FNRI-DOST, 2008). In a nationally representative sample of 7,700 Filipinos age 20 and older, FNRI-DOST reported that very few Filipino adults-only 7% - had high level of leisure – time physical activity. High leisure-time was operationalized in this survey as exercising either “every day” or “three times a week” at 30-45 minutes.

Regular activity provides a number of **physical health benefits**, including lower blood pressure, reduced arthritis pain, weight loss and lowered risk of diabetes. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, getting 150 minutes of moderate exercise – such as biking or brisk walking – or 75 minutes of vigorous exercise each week – such as hiking – help maintain a healthy weight and reduce of chronic disease. Furthermore, **the mental benefits of recreation** lead to an increased confidence, improved creativity and self-esteem according to Lepp. Natural setting rejuvenate and calm the mind, improve outlook and increase positive effect. In addition, the **emotional benefits of recreation reduce** stress, anxiety and depression.

Spending time exercising in a park leads to an increase in positive moods and a reduction in cortisol levels, a hormone release when the body feels stress. Along with an increase in activity, recreation offers the chance to **socialize**, an important benefit in itself. Recreational activity can also increase pride in the community as well as offer the chance to meet people with similar interest, says Kent State University professor Andrew Lepp. (<http://healthyliving.azcentral.com>). There are also **social benefits of recreation**, such as strengthening communities, promoting social bonds and supporting youth. Philippines is large and diverse and has a wide range of social conditions that influence the way we live, work, and recreate. These social conditions can be addressed and improved through participation in park and recreation activities. Recreation opportunities and parks are essential for strengthening and maintaining a health community. (Roggenback, 2011 Learning Benefits of Learning).

Furthermore, social bonds are improved when families recreate together and when seniors and individuals with disabilities are actively engaged in recreation activities. Recreation and park facilities help promote social bonds by uniting families, encouraging cultural sensitivity, and supporting seniors and individuals with disabilities. Recreation provides us with family and community bonds that last a lifetime. These benefits can act in tandem. For example, a recreation program directed at youth obesity can increase self-esteem, reduce the use of alcohol, build family bonds, and promote volunteerism, all at the same time. And, while not the subject of this study, clearly this has a positive economic impact and value to the community as well. The aggregate impact of these health and social benefits makes parks and recreation one of the most cost-effective public services available to decision makers. (Strauss R.S. 2011 Psychosocial Activities in Health Children).

Lastly, research documents disclosed of that the physical, mental, emotional and social benefits of recreation are greatly needed, the information compiled here is important for local and national park and recreation service providers in gathering support for their programs. Educators, law enforcement personnel, and health providers will also benefit from this information and should see park and recreation service providers as active partners in support of their mission, challenge their park and recreation service providers to act on the individual and community benefits demonstrated in this study, and to provide them with proper support. Teachers particularly the public secondary school teachers of San Carlos City Division Office should consider the importance of health and social benefits of recreation. They are challenged to take care their recreation participate as they should engage in the physical and social recreation to stay fit, health and socially supportive to recreational activities. They should therefore increase the level of their awareness on the issue.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the 4th leading cause of disease is inactivity. This is due to the popularity of the technological gadgets and poor health lifestyle. Due to this alarming fact, we must switch into a more active lifestyle by means of engaging to active indoor and outdoor recreation.

In line with CSC Memorandum Circular No. 8, s. 2011 entitled: “**The Great Filipino Workout**”, all elementary and secondary school heads and teachers of San Carlos City Division conduct Physical Fitness and Wellness Activity every Tuesday, Wednesday and Thursday, 4:30 in the afternoon in their respective school ground. This activity aims to promote the importance of a healthy lifestyle and a regimen of regular fitness activity aims to promote the importance of a healthy lifestyle and a regimen of regular fitness activity as strategy to reduce level of risk factors of non-communicable disease (NCD) such as obesity, hypertension, arthritis and diabetes.

The significance of recreational activities improve health condition and help us to use the calories better and sustain a desirable weight. It is best way of preventing illness and early death. Major cause of early death have shifted from infectious diseases to chronic lifestyle-related conditions such as heart diseases cancer and diabetes.

Since the role of teachers in school and society is crucial they should remain healthy and socially fit to be effective builders of the young minds. They must learn to manage their time that no matter how busy they are in school and at home they should find time for relaxation. Recreation and leisure should be apart of their activities. It involves watching television, attending an opera or concert, base jumping, dancing zumba, gardening, picnicking, taking children to the zoo, playing, singing, writing a book and attending social activities in the church and communities. However, based from observation and causal interview from some teachers, they seemed to neglect these areas of life on health and social activities as forms of recreation. They said that they have no more time to perform and due to the insufficient budget to finance these activities. Hence, they should be exposed and informed on the benefits they could get from these recreational activities. This challenged the researcher to conduct the study on the recreational activities of teachers in relation to health benefits to help the teachers enjoy and value the recreational activities.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

This study is based from the Catharsis theory of the Theory of Planned Behavior of Theodorckis (1990).

According to Catharsis Theory, an early explanation of play particularly competitive, active play – serves as a safety valve for the expression of bottled – up emotions. Among the Ancient Greeks, Aristotle saw drama as a means of purging oneself of hostile or aggressive emotions; by vicarious sharing in the stage experience, onlookers purified themselves of harmful feelings. A number of early twentieth – century writers expanded this theory. Harvey Carr, an American psychologist, wrote: “Catharsis...implies the idea of purging or draining of that energy which has antisocial possibilities... The value of football, boxing and other physical contest in relieving the pugnacious tendencies of boys is readily apparent as examples. Catharsis is the act of releasing strong emotion (such as pity or fear) especially by expressing it in an art form. Without the numberless well-organized set forms of play possessed by society which give a harmless outlet to the mischievous and unapplied energy of the young, the task of the teacher and parent would be appalling”. The theory also suggested a vital necessity for active play to help children and youth burn excess energy and provide a socially acceptable channel for aggressive or hostile emotions and drive.

(http://www.jblearning.com/samples/0763749591/49591_Ch02_McLean.pdf)

Furthermore, according to the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1988; Ajzen & Madden, 1986), human behavior is a function of an individual’s intention to perform the behavior in question. In its turn, intention is determined by a combination of three conceptually independent factors: (a) attitude toward the specific behavior, (b) subjected norms, and (c) perceived behavioral control. More specifically, the model proposes that behavior is a function of beliefs, which are related to the behavior. Attitudes are defined as one’s positive or negative predisposition towards a specific behavior, and determined by an individual’s behavioral beliefs toward the behavior (Ajzen, 1988). On the other hand, subjective norm expresses the social pressure that is placed on the individual to perform the specific behavior. Perceived behavioral

control has been introduced to enhance the prediction of behaviors in which volitional control may be incomplete (Ajzen, 1988). Irrespectively of a person's intention, there may be some obstacles preventing him/her from carrying out the behavior. These obstacles may be internal factors, such as, skills, abilities, knowledge and adequate planning, as well as, external factors, such as, time, opportunity, and cooperation with other people (Ajzen & Madden, 1986), and expresses individual beliefs about the ease or difficulty in performing a specific behavior. The TPB postulates that perceived behavior control influences behavior both directly and indirectly through an independent effect on behavioral intention (Ajzen & Madden, 1986). The more it is perceived that the behavior in question is not under control, the more it is expected that a direct link, between perceived behavioral control and behavior, nor mediated by intention, will be present.

In addition, in the context of outdoors, the more positive attitude an individual hold, the higher the societal pressure placed on him. Furthermore, when the behavior is perceived to be controllable, behavioral intentions are more likely to be positive. Participation in outdoor recreational programs has unique characteristics, since it requires for individuals to invest time, effort and energy. Furthermore, there are many internal (e.g., injury risk and perceived fitness and skill levels) and external factors (e.g. weather conditions, transportation, availability of opportunities) that limit individuals' choices and make perceived behavioral control an important variable (Godin, 1993; Michels & Kugler, 1998).

Outdoor recreation and outdoor leisure are generally pursued for a person's enjoyment, whether it be for a sense of relaxation, thrill, developing skills, or being with others and the natural environment.

Outdoor recreational and outdoor leisure activities could include gardening, walking, animal watching, hunting, adventure activities, and so on.

The desire to spend one's time engaged in outdoor recreation and leisure activities for pleasure could well have its roots in psycho-evolutionary theory. Since humans evolved in close connection with nature, there is probably a deep genetic disposition to spending time in natural environments. Even though modern Western human beings live largely in comfortable, artificial environments, they still nevertheless value natural places and often holiday or retire to more natural places.

There may be other desires for participation in outdoor activities, such as for education, personal development, healing, or for employment / survival, but by and large such participation is voluntary and driven by personal values and goals for pleasure / reward.

Conceptual Framework

This study followed the independent and dependent variables scheme of paradigm.

The first box is the independent variable that contains the extent to which teachers engaged in recreational activities along indoor activities, and outdoor activities.

The second box is the dependent variable that contains the health benefits of teachers along: physical, social, mental and emotional.

The third box is the proposed action plan to improve the extent to which teachers engage in recreational activities.

Figure 1. Operational Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the extent to which teachers of San Carlos City Division engage in **Recreational Activities in Relation to Health Benefits** during the school year 2025 – 2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the extent of frequency to which teachers engaged along:
 - a. Indoor Activities
 - b. Outdoor Activities
2. To what extent are the health benefits derived from recreational activities along:
 - a. Physical
 - b. Social
 - c. Emotional
 - d. Mental
3. What is the degree of correlation between the health benefits of indoor recreational activities and outdoor recreational activities of the teacher?
4. What is the degree of seriousness of problems encountered by the teachers in their recreational activities they engaged in?
5. What action plan can be proposed to improve the level of awareness of teachers on the health benefits of recreation.

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no correlation between the health benefits of indoor recreational activities and health benefits of outdoor recreational activities.

Scope and Delimitation

This study dealt on the extent do teachers in Bayambang Division of Pangasinan I engaged in on the health benefits of recreation this school year 2025 – 2026. There were 474 teachers from the 19 public secondary schools of Bayambang Division of Pangasinan I.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study can be beneficial to the following people or group of people.

Curriculum Planners. The proposed action plan can be used by them to improve the

curriculum on health and social recreational particularly in extra-curricular activities in Physical Education and Health Subject. In this way they can eventually make learning more socially meaningful and fruitful.

School Administrators. They can use the results as baseline data for more meaningful, more productive physical and social recreational activities in school to improve the social value of the teachers.

Teachers. They can use the results to receive and reorganize the social and physical activities and integrates them in physical education and health subject.

Guidance Counselors. They can use the results to help teachers to identify ways to stay fit and health.

Researcher. She could have an idea on what is the level of awareness of health and social benefits of recreation and can help improve or respond to right and relevant activities for their recreation.

Future Researchers. They could have an idea on how they can perform similar studies to improve the level of physical and social benefits of recreation for learners.

Definition of Terms

For a clear understanding of this investigation the following terms are defined in relation to the purpose of the study.

Health. It is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease, or infinity (<http://www.who.int/about/definition/en/print.html>). It bring to able function well, physical, mentally, socially and spiritually.

Health benefits. In this study, it refers to the gains from performing physical activities as a part of recreation like rendering obesity, diminishing heart desire, boosting immune system.

Health and social benefits of recreation. These are the benefits of recreation like reduces depression, relieves stress, improves life, self-esteem and reduces wine, unites families, builds cultural diversity and harmony.

Indoor recreational activities. In this study it refers to the activities that are undertaken on the comfort of ones home or more specifically indoor and they are to recreate the mind and soul.

(<https://www.scribd.com/document/124314780/Indoor-Recreational-Activities>)

Mental health benefits. This refers to the benefits that can be derived from it like reduces depression and stress and personal and spiritual growth.

Recreation. In this study it refers to the activities that promotes the link between parks and leisure and better mental, physical, social health of the individual and their communities.

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Recreations. Is an activity of leisure, leisure being discretionary time. The “need to do something for recreation” is an essential element of human biology and psychology. Recreational activities are often done for enjoyment, amusement, or pleasure and are considered to be “fun”.

Social benefits. In this study it refers to the benefits that can be derived from social recreation like strengthening communities, promoting social bonds, and enhancing education as they support youth.

Social Bonds. In this study it refers to the benefits that unites families, supports individual with disabilities, and supports seniors.

Outdoor activities. In this study, it refers to the activity that is undertaken in a natural,

rural or open space outside the confines of buildings usually large land area that is close to nature. (<https://www.buzzle.com/articles/list-of-different-recreational-activities.html>)

Related Literature

Team building activities in the workplace stretch imagination – and are only limited by our imagination and that of our employees. They are remarkable in their ability to foster a sense of community and friendships at work. You need to start offering all of these opportunities to become known as a great workplace.

Low cost, but highly effective team building activities, make your workplace desirable and you an employer of choice. Here are some activities for teambuilding. 1) Lunch discussion and team building groups 2) Provide comfortable collaboration spaces with couches, snacks, and beverages 3) Take an employee to work day 4) Provide group monitoring 5) Sponsor job shadowing opportunities for employees in a different department 6) Provide company sponsorship for sports teams and challenges for charity like half marathons 7) Develop and schedule team building lunch and learns for employees. (<https://www.thebalance.com/team-building-workplace-activities-1919238>).

The World Health Organization (2014) defines physical activity (PA) as an bodily movement that results in increased energy expenditure and is positively correlated with physical health. Physical activity has four general categories: work-related PA (e.g., lifting office supplies), non work-related PA (e.g., doing household chores), travel-related PA (e.g.) walking to a bus terminal), and leisure-related PA (e.g.) going for a morning jog). As a form of leisure-related PA, exercise refers to physical activity that is planned, structured, repetitive, and which maintains or improves physical fitness (Caspersen, Powell, & Christenson, 2005, as cited in Biddle & Mutrie, 2008). It can include activities such as running, swimming, gym-based fitness activities, and recreational sport.

Clinical studies suggest that relaxation techniques may be beneficial in patients with generalized anxiety, obsessive compulsive disorder, social phobias, or panic disorders, although these approaches do not appear to be as effective as psychotherapy. Many of the studies show that relaxations techniques were more effective as psychotherapy. Many of the studies show that relaxations techniques were more effective when used in conjunction with cognitive or behavioral therapy techniques (Ost L., 2000). Relaxation has also shown some effectiveness in treating individuals with anger, hostility, and aggressive behavior. It is not clear if effects of relaxation therapy are long-term. If a person stops practicing the deep-breathing exercises, the symptoms of stress may return. While relaxation techniques may be used for conditions related to stress management, there is not enough evidence to form firm conclusions about the effectiveness of relaxation for other, more severe mental conditions (Ost L., 2000).

There is debate about how to define leisure. However, there is a general consensus that there are three primarily ways in which to consider leisure. First, Leisure as Time which define as a leisure that is free from obligations, work (paid and unpaid), and tasks required for existing (sleeping, eating). Leisure time is residual time. Some people argue it is the constructive use of free time. While many may view free times as all nonworking hours, only a small amount of time spent away from work is actually free from other obligations that are necessary for existence, such as sleeping and eating. (Jones and Bartlet (2010). Second is leisure as activity which can also be viewed as activities that people engage in during their free time – activities that are not work oriented or that do not involve life maintenance tasks such as housecleaning or

sleeping. Leisure as activity encompasses the activities that we engage in for reason as varied as relaxation, competition, or growth and may include reading for pleasure, meditating, painting and participating in sports. Certain activities qualify as leisure because they take place during time away from work and are not engaged in for existence. However, as has been argued by many, it is extremely difficult to come up with a list of activities that everyone agrees represents leisure – to some an activity might be a leisure activity and to others it might not necessarily be a leisure activity. Therefore, with this definition the line between work and leisure is not clear in that what is leisure to some may be work to others and vice versa. Lastly, leisure as State of Mind which is different from leisure as time or activity by which leisure as state of mind is much more subjective in that it considers the individuals perceptions of an activity. Concepts such as perceived freedom, intrinsic motivation, perceived competence, and positive affect are critical to determining whether an experience is leisure or not leisure (Laura Payne). According to Laura Payne, **perceived freedom** refers to an individual's ability to choose the activity or experience in that the individual is free from other obligations as well as has the freedom to act without control from others while **intrinsic motivation**, means that the person is moved from within to participate. The person is not influenced by external factors (e.g., people or reward) and the experience results in personal feelings of satisfaction, enjoyment, and gratification. Another concept is the **perceived competence** which refers to the skills people believed they possess and whether their skill levels are in line with the degree of challenge inherent in an experience.

What may be a leisure experience for one person may not be for another, whether an experience is leisure depends on many factors. Enjoyment, motivation, and choice are three of the most important of these factors. Therefore, when different individuals engage in the same activity, their state of mind can differ drastically.

Play is imaginative, intrinsically motivated, non-serious, freely chosen, and actively engaging. While most people see play as the domain of children, adults also play, although often their play is more entwined with rules and regulations, which calls into question how playful their play really is. On the other hand, children's play is typified by spontaneity, joyfulness, and inhibition and is done not as a means to an end but for its inherent pleasure.

There were some consensus on the definition of recreation. Recreation is an activity that people engage in during their free time, that people enjoy, and that people recognize as having socially redeeming values. Unlike leisure, recreation has a connotation of being morally acceptable not just to the individual but also to society as a whole, and thus we program for those activities within the context. While recreation activities can take many forms, they must contribute to society in a way that society deems acceptable. This means that activities deemed socially acceptable for recreation can change over time. Examples of recreational activities are endless and include sports, music, games, travel, reading, arts and crafts, and dance. The specific activity performed is less important than the reason for performing the activity, which is the outcome. For most the overarching desired outcome is recreation or restoration. Participants hope that their recreation pursuits can help them to balance their lives and refresh themselves from their work as well as other mandated activities such as housecleaning, child rearing, and so on. (<http://www.humankinetics.com.ph>).

The Philippines is currently facing major health issues with alarming increases in the prevalence of hypertension, obesity, and physical inactivity according to national data (Food and Nutrition Research Institute, Department of Science and Technology [FNRI-DOST], 2008). In a nationally representative sample of 7,700 Filipinos ages 20 and older, FNRI-DOST reported that

very few Filipino adults – only 7% - had high levels of leisure – time physical activity. High leisure – time PA was operationalized in this survey as exercising either “everyday” or “three to five times a week” at 30 – 45 minutes.

People also see recreation as a social instrument because of its contribution to society. That is, professionals have long used recreation programs and services to produce socially desirable outcomes, such as the wise use of free time, physical fitness, and positive youth development. The organized development of recreation programs to meet a variety of physical, psychological, and social needs has led to recreation playing a role as a social instrument for well-being and, in some cases, change. This role has been the impetus for the development of many recreation providers from municipalities to nonprofits such as YMCA, YWCA, Boy Scout, girl Scouts, and the Boys and Girl Clubs. There are also for-profit agencies, such as fitness centers and spas, design to provide positive outcomes.

There are tons of recreational activities that people, regardless of age, can take part in and enjoy with friends and family members. Here is a Buzzle article that will give you some examples of such activities. While caught in the rut of hectic jobs and routine chores, everyone needs some time to rejuvenate their minds and bodies, and indulge in these activities. First, we have indoor activities which includes reading, writing, computer and video games, internet surfing, dancing and indoor games like table tennis, badminton or chess. The benefits of indoor recreation is not only a great source of entertainment, but also a vast source of knowledge and inspiration. Another activity is the outdoor recreational activities which includes camping, fishing, sailing, skateboarding, swimming, and surfing. It is an excellent way to relax yourself as well as a fun workout to keep you healthy. In addition to the aforementioned activities you can always indulge in various outdoor sports like cricket, golf, football, baseball, or basketball. Recreation time is all about having beautiful moments in your life, creating memories that you can reminisce and smile about. <http://www.buzzle.com/article/types-of-recreation.html>

No one would ever understand the importance of recreation till the time they experience the value and benefits of its on their own. It is more of a fun embodied in the form of activities to refresh one’s body and mind. While type of recreation varies from individual to individual, spending time in something that rock your senses is an experience in itself. The form of recreation include from simplest of listening to music to the likes of parachuting or bungee jumping. Excess of recreation is called escapism and is something that distract you from your main purpose and affects your time too. A well blended mixture of work and recreation is excellent recipe that keeps you going on the path to success.

The Values and Benefits of Recreation for professional are numerous. The charm lies in looking out something that’s works out best for you. There are different types of recreation and what value and benefit you derive from it depends upon your proactiveness to try them out and incorporate them as part of working routine. The 10 values and benefits that work out best and should encourage you to take recreational activities from time to time: 1) Helps You Relax, 2) Reduces Stress, 3) Refresh the Senses, 4) Refills the Energy, 5) Quality of Life, 6) Build Family Unity, 7) Build Self-esteem, 8) Reduce Stress, 9) Promote Sensitivity to Cultural Diversity, and 10) Increase community Pride-Strengthen Neighborhood Involvement.

Physical active older people typically benefit from lower blood pressure, increase muscle strength, jointly flexibility, and lower total cholesterol levels than do less active people. Leisure activities can provide for the creation of new social relationships for Seniors after the loss of a loved one. Someone turns 50 every 8.4 seconds. By 2005, it is estimated one in five Americans

will be 65 and older. In the National Recreation Policy Statement, the federal and provincials governments of Canada define recreation as: “all activity chosen by a person or group to make leisure time more interesting, more enjoyable and more satisfying”. Recreation is the positive actions and choices we make to recreate, to restore and refresh body, mind and spirit.

Recreation is unique in its ability to build capacity – the personal, social, economic, and environmental benefits of recreation are the essence of a healthy community and individual well-being. Recreation creates opportunities for people to be active, offering diverse and enjoyable ways to stay health.

The benefits of recreation can help make communities a more vital, cohesive place – a place that can solve its own problems, achieve its own dreams and build its own culture. Made be shared, recreation often unites people and equips them to build community. Recreation: Unites communities and neighborhoods – adding to identify and pride, Develops opportunities for volunteerism, Promotes ethnic and cultural harmony, Engages community organizations in positive and creative contributions to their community and Boosts sustainable economic development by attracting residents, business, and tourist seeking quality of live. Meanwhile, the social benefits to recreation changes strangers into neighbors, bringing people together in settings where friendship and abilities can grow in a positive environment. In a time when computers, cars and other labour saving devices have weakened or replaced human contact, recreation may improve health just as much by building social supports as by enhancing physical health. Recreation: Combats isolation and loneliness, Strengthens families, Encourages learning, Develop social skills.

Regular, moderate physical activity when coupled with healthy eating offers a positive solution to obesity and ill health. Recreation is one of the best medicines money can buy. Recreation provides diverse opportunities and choices for individuals to participate in that: combats chronic conditions such as diabetes, arthritis, asthma and osteoporosis, Helps manage blood pressure, cholesterol levels, Increases life expectancy, Improves cardiovascular and respiratory functions, Increases muscular strength and endurance and Significantly reduces rate of heart disease, stroke and certain cancers.

In the 1950s and 1960s, activities such as horseback trail riding, skiing, snowmobiling and taking a day hike were among some of the popular choices among outdoor enthusiasts. While these are still enjoyed, people have been leaning toward less vigorous physical activities since that time. According to H. Ken Cordell of the U.S. Forest Service. Yet incorporating physical activity into your leisure and recreation activities is an ideal way to fit more exercise into your schedule – as well as address your mental wellness. Taking part in recreational activities, particularly outdoors, can improve your physical wellness. In fact, people who frequently take advantage of park activities have fewer doctor visits, lower body mass indexes and lower systolic blood pressures than those who don’t, according to Dr. Laura L. Payne of the University of Illinois. A 2005 California State Parks report also highlights that outdoor recreation provides an excellent opportunity to increase exercise. It cites (2010) stud revealing that the availability of recreational facilities in a location impacts the amount of physical activity in which residents participate.

Mental wellness is an important part of your overall health and can impact your physical well-being. Participating in leisure and recreation activities can help you better manage stress and reduce depression. Leisure provides you the chance to find balance in your life; it also puts you in control of how you’re spending you time, which is an important consideration because

you may feel overwhelmed by obligations. Taking part in leisure activities as a family is also beneficial for your kids because you're modeling healthy ways to handle stress and emotions. Participating in leisure activities regularly reduces depression; in fact, just thinking about past outdoor recreation experience can improve mood, according to the 2005 California State Parks report.

Finding balance is also a reason why leisure and recreation can enhance your quality of life. Physical recreation, in particular, is associated with improved self-esteem. In addition, you're more likely to feel satisfied about your life when you regularly take in recreation activities. This has significant implications for your mental health and, in turn, your physical health. In fact, 90 percent of respondents in a 2000 American Recreation Coalition study reported being satisfied with their health and fitness. In contrast, 60 percent of those who didn't take part in such activity reported not being satisfied with their health and fitness.

All of these health benefits explain why recreational therapy can be such an essential part of a rehabilitation program. This type of therapy involves using various recreation or leisure activities to enhance or promote wellness. The American Therapeutic Recreation Association shines a spotlight on some of the benefits for the populations that commonly take advantage of the therapy including psychiatric patients, recovering addicts, children and seniors. Some of these benefits include faster healing from medical conditions, stress management, improved body function and better cognitive function.

Social Benefits of Recreation (Source: Parks and Recreational Ontario)

Leisure provides leadership opportunities that build strong communities. Community recreation services reduce alienation and anti-social behaviors. Integrated and accessible leisure services are critical to the quality of life of people with a disability or disadvantage. Leisure opportunities and facilities are the foundations of community pride.

Health Benefits of Recreation (Source: Parks and Recreational Ontario)

Regular physical activity is one of the very best methods of health insurance. Physical recreation and fitness contributes to a full and meaningful life. Children's play is essential to the human development process. Relaxation, rest and vitalization through the opportunity for leisure is essential to stress management in our busy world.

Discriminatory provision of recreation services. Lack of recreation funds. Underdeveloped leisure facilities. Inadequate leisure facilities. Under designated recreational space.

As a world population ages and working hours decline, the use of leisure time assumes growing importance. This is a completely new phenomenon to the post-industrial revolution urban society. In traditional rural cultural, community festivities and religious rites involves all ages and gave meaningful roles to young and old alike. The shrine, cathedral, village green, community plaza and so on have few contemporary equivalents. Furthermore, those equivalents that do exist – such as sports centres and theatres – cater to very delimited segments of the population, and are often exorbitantly expensive, especially for those whose income is limited by retirement. Public centres are too often such a low budget priority that facilities, staffing and programming is severely limited.

Related Studies

There are lots of studies about recreational activities among teachers in the Philippines. According to Roxas, 2009, the teachers are not easily affected by the difficulties that they encounter in relation to their job. Seemingly, they have a high level of stress tolerance. The primary sources of stress experienced by the teachers in Baguio City in order of prevalence are as follows: 1) large class sizes, 2) excessive paperwork or documentation, and 3) inadequacy of resources, materials and equipment to do the job. In contrast, the least prevalent sources of stress experiences and ranked last among the indicators are as follows: increased level of competition among colleagues, colleagues undermining competence or personality, and not airing of personal opinion.

Similarly, Betonio (2015), determined the factors of recreational activity of the college faculty experienced in terms of Work related, Peer related, Family related, Economic related, Schools' Policies related and Management Practices related stresses. His study entitled "Recreation and the Teaching Performance of the College Faculty" also look into the level of effectiveness of the faculty in their teaching performance in terms of Classroom Management, Communication Skills, Facilitating Students Learning, Evaluation and Teacher Student relationship. Results showed that the faculty experienced moderate level of stress in the areas of Economic related stress, Schools' Policies and Management Practices stresses and experienced low level of stress with Work and Peer related stresses. The overall rating of the effectiveness of the performance of the faculty in all parameters were very satisfactory which means there is still room for improvement to make it an outstanding assessment.

Likewise, Mingo, 2017, also studied about recreational activities of teachers. His study showed that factors that elementary and high school teachers perceived to cause them less recreational activities are a combination of work-related (too much paperwork, oversized classes, further studies, non-teaching duties, incompetent superiors), personal factors (relationships, age-related, i.e., stages in life, death in the family, etc.) and economics (insufficient salary, high cost of living). Their common activities are passive entertainment like watching television or going to the movies. Window shopping is also a common de-stressor. Although the method mentioned are positive most of them are sedentary.

Lastly, Narciso, 2017, research about relationship between recreational activities and performance of teachers. In his study, "Recreational Activity and Performance of Um Tagum College Faculty", results implied that the level of Recreational activity is moderate. Furthermore, the level of work performance is high. Through non-experimental quantitative research using correlation technique, validated questionnaire, Mean and Standard Deviation and Pearson r , results revealed that no significant relationship existed between work and recreational activities Tagum College Faculty.

Chapter 2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Descriptive – correlational method was used in the study. Descriptive correlation design, it is a design which uses some form of correlation to describe data, but does not seek to find whether it is a statistically significant relationship. Correlation method is to examine relationships between variables. Descriptive - correlation method according to Greene (2007) describes and interprets the data. It is composed of the condition of relationship that exists,

practices that prevail, beliefs, process that are going on and efforts that are being felt and developing. It is appropriate method to be used since it described extent of teachers engage in recreational activities and correlate them on the health benefits.

Locale and Population of the Study

This study was conducted in public secondary schools in Bayambang Pangasinan I Division. The respondents were the 320 teachers coming from 27 public elementary schools of Bayambang Elementary Schools, Pangasinan I Division taken in complete enumeration.

Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents by school.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Schools	No. of Teachers	School Heads
1. Amancosiling Elementary School	17	1
2. Ambayat Integrated School	10	1
3. A.P. Guevara Integrated School	8	1
4. Bascos – Manambang Parte Elementary School	12	1
5. Buayaen Central School	18	1
6. Carungay Elementary School	9	1
7. Cason Elementary School	20	1
8. Catalino Castañeda Elementary School	17	1
9. Caturay Elementary School	9	1
10. Daraway Elementary School	6	1
11. Dosoc Elementary School	10	1
12. Hermoza Elementary School	17	1
13. Inirangan Elementary School	15	1
14. Malioer Elementary School	10	1
15. Managos Elementary School	10	1
16. Manambaong Sur Elementary School	11	1
17. Obillo Elementary School	7	1
18. Pangdel Elementary School	12	1
19. Paragos Elementary School	8	1
20. San Gabriel-Iton Elementary School	13	1
21. San Gabriel 2 nd Elementary School	15	1
22. San Vicente Elementary School	13	1
23. Tampog Elementary School	9	1
24. Tatarac-Apalen Elementary School	13	1
25. Telbang Elementary School	10	1
26. Warding Elementary School	8	1
27. Wawa Elementary School	13	1
Total	320	27

Data Gathering Instrument

This study will use the questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument taken from the Health and Social Benefits of Recreation: **An Element of the California Outdoor Recreation Planning Chairman Program by: Arnold Schwarzenegger**. It consists of the following parts.

Part 1 on the different recreational activities classified into: 1. Indoor activities, 2. Outdoor activities.

Part 2 is on the health benefits classified into: 1. Physical, 2. Social, 3. Emotional, 4. Mental.

Part 3 is on the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by teachers in engaging with the different recreational activities.

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission was sought first from the Schools Division Superintendent of Pangasinan I Division, Dr. Fatima Boado then to the school principals of public secondary schools of Bayambang, Division of Pangasinan. After that she prepared a number of copies of the questionnaire and administered them to all respondents and retrieve the same. She will personally administer and retrieve the instrument with the help of some teachers close to her to ensure 100 percent retrieval.

It took her 3 weeks to administer and retrieve the instrument due to the intervening activities in the school that affected the availability of the respondents.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data were statistically treated to obtain answers to the stated problems.

Problem 1 on determining the extent to which teachers engaged in recreational activities.

		Descriptive	Interpretative
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very High Extent	Always
4	3.41 – 4.20	High	Sometimes
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	Moderate
2	1.81 – 2.60	Fair	Fair
1	1.00 – 1.80	Low	Never

Problem 2 on determining the level of health benefits 5-value likert scale with average weighted mean (AWM) descriptive rating: 5 – very high, 4 – high, 3 – moderate, 2 – low, 1 – very low.

Problem 3 on determining significant correlation between health benefits of outdoor recreational activities and indoor recreational activities Pearson's r with descriptive interpretation was used.

The formula is:

$$r = \frac{n\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2} \sqrt{n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}}$$

where:

n = the sample size

$$\begin{aligned} \sum x &= \text{the total observations under variable } x \\ \sum y &= \text{the total observations under variable } y \\ \sum xy &= \text{the sum of the squares of observations under the paired variables } x \text{ and } y \\ \sum x^2 &= \text{the sum of the squares of observations under variable } x \\ \sum y^2 &= \text{the sum of the squares of observations under variable } y \end{aligned}$$

Chapter 3

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of data gathered by the researcher through the use of the questionnaire.

Table 2 presents the extent do the teachers engage in indoor activities as perceived themselves.

Table 2
Extent to which Teachers Engage in Indoor Activities

Indoor Activities	AWM N=474	Interpretation	DE
1. Dancing (Ballroom / zumba)	3.30	Sometimes	ME
2. Going to the gym	2.50	Rarely	LE
3. Healthy diet / nutrition	2.70	Sometimes	ME
4. Enough sleep	3.50	Often	HE
5. Doing sit ups	1.80	Never	VLE
6. Doing yoga	1.30	Never	VLE
7. Drinking at least 8 glass of water	3.90	Often	HE
8. Family spending time together	4.10	Often	HE
9. Reading books, newspapers, magazines	3.15	Sometimes	ME
10. Writing Biography / Literacy	1.90	Rarely	LE
11. Computer and video games	1.70	Never	VLE
12. Internet surfing (facebook, etc.)	2.40	Sometimes	ME
13. Music plays/Musical/Drama	2.20	Rarely	LE
14. Watching or Seeing Movies	4.15	Often	LE
Overall AWM	2.76	Sometimes	ME

5	4.21 – 5.00	Very High Extent (VHE)
4	3.41 – 4.20	High Extent (HE)
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate Extent (ME)
2	1.81 – 2.60	Low Extent (LE)
1	1.00 – 2.60	Very Low Extent (VLE)

Data showed that the teachers engaged in the following indoor activities in a low extent perceived by their weighted mean: going to the gym 2.50; writing a biography / literary 1.90; and watching musical play/drama 2.20. It meant that the teachers had the time needed to do them. There were several indoor activities which were engaged in a very low extent such as doing sit ups 1.80; doing yoga 1.30; and computer and video games 1.70. It meant that teachers differently engaged in these indoor activities because they need skills, discipline, and time and

yet they were not so common ones like the others.

Looking further at the data, it could be noted that the teachers engaged to a high extent in the following indoor activities: enough sleep 3.50; drinking at least 8 glasses of water, spending time with their family 4.10 and watching or seeing movies 4.15. It meant that teachers gave much value to them and they implied that these were common and very common to thesis.

As a whole, it could be gleaned that the teachers moderately engaged with the indoor activities proven by the total average weighted mean of 2.76. It meant that they had been engaging in the indoor activities as a part of their routine but not so much energized due to the nature their school, home and community. It implied throughout that their engagement on these activities was affected by their time and so they failed to highly engaged in them.

Outdoor Activities

Table 3 presents the extent do the teachers engage in outdoor activities as perceived by themselves.

Table 3
Extent to which the Teachers Engage in Outdoor Activities

Outdoor Activities	AWM	DE
1. Physical exercises (jogging, running, etc.)	2.30	LE
2. Playing ball games like basketball, volleyball, etc.	2.45	LE
3. Biking	2.50	LE
4. Hiking	2.10	LE
5. Swimming	2.13	LE
6. Surfing	1.20	VLE
7. Sailing / boating	1.05	VLE
8. Going out with friends	4.20	HE
9. Visiting sick person in the hospital	3.39	ME
10. Joining some religious, non-profit organization	4.15	HE
11. Visit museums	2.10	LE
12. Performing charitable acts	2.30	LE
Overall AWM	2.49	ME

Analyzing the data further, it could be said that going out with friends 4.20; going to the religious non-profit organization, were highly engaged by the teachers. It meant that these were a common activities and enjoyed to perform activities and found high regard of values in them.

As a whole their engagement in outdoor activities was to the moderate extent proven by total average weighted mean of 2.49. It meant that their engaged over minimal. It implied that they were constraint by their nature of work, time they need, and budget in performing them.

Table 4 presents the summary of Recreational Activities Teacher Engaged in Outdoor Activities

Table 4
Summary of Recreational Activities of Teachers Engaged in Outdoor Activities

Recreational Activities	AWM	DE
Indoor Activities	2.76	ME
Outdoor Activities	2.49	ME

It could be noted that the indoor activities of teachers were rated by them to moderate extent. It meant that they engaged constantly in these outdoor activities as moderate extent. The findings imply that the minimum engagement with their indoor and outdoor activities were affected by their time and kind of work they have in school, home and community.

Level of Health Benefits of Recreational Activities

Physical Health Benefits

Table 5 presents the level of Perceived benefits of recreational activities along physical benefit as perceived by themselves.

Table 5
Level of Perceived Benefits of Recreational Activities
Along Physical Health

I. The Physical Health Benefits	Indoor		Outdoor	
	AWM	DE	AWM	DE
1. Reduces obesity	4.14	H	4.15	H
2. Diminishes chronic diseases	4.1	H	4.10	H
3. Diminishes risk of heart diseases	4	VH	4.30	VH
4. Diminishes risk of diabetes	4.05	H	4.05	H
5. Diminishes risk of cancer	3.1	M	3.10	M
6. Diminishes osteoporosis	3.05	M	3.05	M
7. Boosts immune system	3.18	M	3.18	M
8. Increase life expectancy	2.70	M	2.70	M
TOTAL AWM	3.54	H	3.58	H

Table 5 showed that the teachers found that indoor and outdoor health benefits of recreational activities along physical health very high in terms of diminishing risk of heart disease. It meant that they recognized physical health benefit of recreational activities. They also believed that the activities could reduce obesity, chronic disease, and diminishes risk of diabetes which were rated high. The findings implied that the respondents found the benefits of recreational activities helpful in achieving healthy body and healthy mind to be fit for work.

Looking at the data in detail, it could be seen that the physical health benefits of recreational activities were really high. It meant that their experiences led them to practice them as they engage in the activities daily. It implied that there was a high sense of adherence to the value of recreational activities as they boost immune system and increase life expectancy.

Mental Health Benefit

Table 6 presents the benefits of recreational activities along mental health.

Table 6
Health Benefits of Recreational Activities Along Mental Health

II. Mental Health Benefits	Indoor		Outdoor	
	AWM	DE	AWM	DE
1. Reduces depression	4.01	H	3.90	H
2. Relieves stress	4.13	H	4.15	H
3. Improve quality life	3.29	M	3.25	M
4. Improve self-esteem	3.12	M	3.15	M
5. Improves personal and spiritual growth	2.30	L	2.50	L
6. Improves life satisfaction	2.80	L	2.60	L
TOTAL AWM	3.28	M	3.26	M

Table 6 Mental Health Benefits

It could be noted that indoor recreational activities had high mental health benefits in relieving stress with an average weighted mean of 4.13 and in reducing depression which is 4.15. The teachers found a low in case of improving personal and spiritual growth, and improved the satisfaction which is 2.30 and 2.80 weighted mean respectively. Two of the indicators were moderate as in improves quality life and improves self-esteem 3.29 and 3.12 weighted mean. The findings implied that the teacher found the recreational activities is common in improving mental health. Moreover, in outdoor recreational activities, mental health benefits in relieving stress with an average weighted mean of 4.15 and in reducing depression which is 3.90 is high. The teachers found at low in case of improving personal and spiritual growth, and improves the satisfaction which is 2.50 and 2.60 weighted mean respectively. Two of the indicators were moderate as in improves quality life and improves self-esteem 3.25 and 3.15 weighted mean. The findings implied that the teacher found the recreational activities were common in improving mental health.

As a whole, the mental health benefits of recreational activities both indoor and outdoor was found by the teachers moderate. It meant that the recreational activities did not affect their mental health so much. It implied that they believed them to be mediocre in benefits.

Social Benefits of Recreation

Table 7 presents the health benefits of recreational activities along social benefits.

Table 7
Health Benefits of Recreational Activities Along Social Benefits

III. Social Benefits of Recreation	Indoor		Outdoor	
	AWM	DE	AWM	DE
1. Strengths of communities				
a. It reduces crime	2.70	M	2.70	M
b. It encourages volunteerism	1.60	VL	1.80	VL
c. It promotes stewardship	1.25	VL	1.25	VL
	1.85	VL	1.92	VL
2. Promotes social bonds				
a. It unites families	4.40	VH	4.50	VH

b. It builds cultural diversity and harmony	4.30	VH	4.20	VH
c. It supports individual with disabilities	2.70	M	2.70	M
d. It supports senior citizens	1.80	L	1.95	L
	3.30	M	3.34	L
3. Supports youth				
a. It develops the youth	3.20	H	2.60	H
b. It enhances education	2.40	L	2.55	L
c. It deters negative behaviors	3.10	M	3.20	M
d. It decrease drugs, alcohol use and early sexual activity	3.10	M	3.40	M
e. It prevents crime.	3.00	M	3.30	M
	2.96	M	3.21	M
Total AWM	2.70	M	2.82	M

Social Benefit of Recreation

Data revealed that in indoor and outdoor recreational activities, encouraging voluntarism, and promoting stewardship had very low social benefits. Furthermore, supporting senior citizen and enhancing education were low in social benefits. It means that they did not find social benefits in terms of education and support to senior citizens particularly in encouraging volunteerism and promoting stewardship.

However, the teachers believed that social benefits of recreation in indoor and outdoor activities in uniting youths and building cultural diversity and harmony. It meant that the recreational moderately by the teachers such as reduces crime, supports individual with disabilities, deterred negative behaviors, decrease drugs, alcohol use and early sexual activity, and prevents crime. It means that they were ordinary source of strengthening community, provides several bonds, and supports youths.

As a whole, the teachers perceived the social benefits of recreation moderately beneficial. As proven by the total of average weighted mean of 2.82. It meant that they were mediocre in social benefits. It implied that the teachers failed to explore and experience highly what social recreation can give to do in social bonds, community harmony, and social principles of exercises.

Emotional Benefits of Recreation

Table 8 presents the level of health benefits of indoor and outdoor recreational activities along emotional dimension as perceived by the teachers themselves.

Table 8
Health Benefits of Recreational Activities Along Emotional Dimension

IV. Emotional Benefits of Recreation	Indoor		Outdoor	
	AWM	DE	AWM	DE
1. Reduces stress	4.1	H	4.15	H
2. Reduces anxiety and depression	4	H	4.20	H
3. Increase in positive moods	3	M	3.35	M
4. Reduction in cortisol level, a hormone released	3	M	3.30	M

when the body feels stress.				
5. Increase accessed to green space for activities such as walking decrease stress specially for children.	4	H	4.15	H
Total AWM	3.62	H	3.83	H

It could be noted that in indoor and outdoor recreational activities, the emotional benefits of recreation is high in terms of reducing stress, anxiety and depression, and increasing accesses to green space for activities such as walking, decreasing stress especially for children. It was moderate however, in reducing cholesterol level, hormone release when the body feels stress.

As a whole, it could be deduced that the emotional benefits or recreation was high proven by the overall weighted mean of 3.62 in indoor recreational activities while the overall weighted mean for outdoor recreational activities is 3.83. The findings mean that recreation could bring emotional stability and positive health benefits for these engage on it. It implies that the teachers are aware of the benefits derived from recreation and therefore they can engage in such activities.

Summary of the Health Benefits of Recreational Activities

Table 9 presents the summary of the health benefits of indoor recreational activities and outdoor recreational activities as perceived by the teachers in terms of physical, social, mental and emotional benefits.

Table 9
Summary of Health Benefits of Recreational Activities

Health Benefits	Indoor		Outdoor	
	AWM	DE	AWM	DE
Physical	4.54	VH	3.58	H
Social	3.28	M	2.82	M
Mental	2.70	M	3.26	M
Emotional	3.62	H	3.83	H
Total AWM	3.54	H	3.37	M

It could be noted that in indoor activities, physical benefits is very high, emotional benefits was high, while social and mental benefits are moderate. Meanwhile, in outdoor recreational activities indicates that physical and emotional benefits are high, while social and mental benefits are moderate, Therefore, the findings imply that they found the recreational activities indoor or outdoor as beneficial to physical and emotional self.

As a whole the benefits of recreational activities were rated High in indoor and moderate in outdoor. It meant that the teachers found the activities highly important to their physical, social, mental, and emotional well-being.

Table 10
Significant Correlation Between the Health Benefits of Indoor Recreational Activities and the Outdoor Recreational Activities

Health Benefits	Recreational Activities		Degree of Correlation
	Indoor	Outdoor	
Physical	4.54	3.52	0.97
Social	3.28	2.82	
Mental	2.70	3.26	
Emotional	3.62	3.83	

There was a significant correlation between the health benefits gain in performing indoor activities and health benefits gain in performing indoor activities. This implied that the health benefits gained from outdoor activities are tantamount to the health benefits gained from indoor activities. Moreover, engaging such recreational activities either indoor or outdoor could benefit health to high extent.

Problem Met by Teachers

Table 11 presents the degree of dimension of the problem in the recreational activities they engaged in.

Table 11
Degree of Seriousness of the Problems in Engaging in the Different Recreational Activities

Problems	AWM	DE	RANK
1. Lack of time in engaging to the recreational activities.	2.90	S	1
2. Lack of financial resources to finance them.	2.25	MS	6.5
3. Poor recreational facilities and equipment.	2.75	S	2
4. Lack of awareness on the health and social benefits of recreations.	2.30	MS	5
5. Poor social integration of teachers due to volume of work in school and home.	2.25	MS	6.5
6. Poor health condition of the teachers.	1.60	LS	10
7. Lack of motivation and interests on social and health benefits.	2.20	MS	8.5
8. Under designated recreational space.	2.35	S	4
9. Ineffective utilization of public environment	2.20	MS	8.5
10. Discriminatory prociasion of recreation resources.	2.40	S	3
Total AWM	2.28	MS	

The table revealed that 4 problems were rated serious such as lack of time in engaging to the recreational activities poor recreational space, and discriminatory use of recreational resources. There were 5 indicators which were rated moderately serious like: lack of awareness on the health and social benefits of recreation of poor social integration of teachers, and lack of financial resources to finance them, one of the problem was rated least serious which is poor health condition of the teacher. The findings implied that the teachers didn't have enough and condition to engage in recreational activities to become socially, emotionally and physically healthy.

The whole table disclosed that the problems encountered by the teachers were moderately serious proven by the overall average weighted mean of 2.28. It meant that they were affected by the problems to pursue their recreational activities. It implied that the problems were impeachment to the right use of recreation and enjoy the benefits thereof.

Proposed Action Plan to Improve the Recreational Activities of Teachers

I. Rationale

The world today is confronted with a number of serious health and social issues – obesity, diabetes, depression and suicide to name a few. The trend towards a sedentary lifestyle is recognized as a major contributor towards many of world's health and social issues.

Many of our activities are less physically active that it does not need to extra effort and energy but others are physically active that requires to burn extra calories. The activities that voluntarily participate in during free tie are called Recreation. In choosing recreational activities, it should be of our interest, also voluntary and not pressured by somebody and lastly it should meet our recreational satisfaction needs.

Since the role of teachers in school and society is crucial they should remain healthy and socially fit to be effective builders of the young minds. They should be exposed and informed on the benefits they could get from these indoor and outdoor recreational activities.

II. Introduction

The plan of action formulated in tabular form for recreational activities. It is composed of the following parts.

1. Areas of Concern
2. Goals / Objectives
3. Strategies / Activities
4. Time Frame
5. People Involved
6. Budget / Source
7. Success Indicators

The plan of action proper presented in detail can be found in the preceding pages.

Areas of Concern	Goals and Objectives	Strategies / Activities	Time Frame	People Involved	Budget / Source	Success Indicator
1. Lack of time in engaging recreational activities	Engage participant in recreational activities	Conduct team building activities	December	Teachers, School Head	P20,000	90% of the teachers shall have attended team building activities.
2. Poor recreational facilities and equipment.	Purchase facilities and equipment for recreational activities	Fundraising activities Solicit from stakeholder	Year round	Teachers, School Head, Stakeholder Community	P40,000	90% shall have purchased facilities and equipment for

						recreational activities.
3. Discriminatory in the use of recreational activities	Increase the level awareness of the participant in maximizing the use of recreational activities	Conduct seminar about the use of recreational activities	Year round as scheduled	Teachers, School Head Lecturers	P20,000	90% of the teachers shall have increased the level awareness of recreational activities.
4. Under designated recreational space./	Provide enough space for recreational activities	Tap the assistance of the LGU's for sponsorship	Year round	Teachers, School Head Stakeholder Community	P30,000	90% shall have provided enough space for recreational activities.
5. Lack of awareness on the health and social benefits of recreational activities	Increase the level of awareness on the health and social benefits of recreational activities	Conduct trainings, seminars and workshops on the health and social benefits of recreational activities	Year round	Teachers, School Head Lecturers	P20,000	90% of the teachers shall have increase the level of awareness on the health and social benefits of recreational activities.

Chapter 4

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter represents the summary of findings, conclusion and recommendation based from analysis of data gathered through the questionnaire.

Summary of the Findings

This study determined the extent to which public elementary school teachers of Bayambang Division of Pangasinan I engaged in recreational activities in relation to health benefits during the school year 2025 – 2026.

Findings

The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. The teachers moderately engaged in both indoor activities and outdoor activities of recreation.
2. The recreational activities were highly beneficial to physical and emotional aspects; moderately beneficial in social and mental aspects.
3. There was a very high correlation between the health benefits of the teachers gained in performing indoor recreational activities and outdoor recreational activities.
4. The problems encountered by the respondent teachers along recreational activities were described as moderately serious.
5. The proposed plan of action can be formulated.

Conclusions

The following conclusion were drawn from the findings of the study:

1. The teachers have not reached the desired extent of engaging recreational activities.
2. The teachers found the recreational activities beneficial to their physical, social, mental and emotional well-being.
3. The health benefits aimed from indoor recreational activities and outdoor recreational activities were related to each other.
4. The formulated action plan could improve the extent of teachers engage in recreational activities in relation to health benefits.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based from the conclusions of the study.

1. The proposed plan of action shall be endorsed to the school, Division Superintendent of Pangasinan I and recommend it to the different schools for implementation.
2. Further research on the problem shall be conducted to other Divisions to improve the findings the present study.
3. Teachers must always find time to have relaxation and have indiscriminate program relative to all recreational activities to stay fit in performing the duties as teacher.
4. The school and community must join to plan meaningful time to engage in recreational activities for the whole school and community to make more activities for all.

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